

Socio-technical factors generating social debt

Table 5: Cultural and organizational factors.

Id	Cause and Primary studies
COF1	Absence of values and norms aligned with organizational objectives [PS2, PS9].
COF2	Deficient interaction among team members [PS2, PS21].
COF3	Reduced communication leading to misunderstandings and misalignment with project and organizational goals [PS2, PS21].
COF4	Social distance resulting from rigid organizational hierarchies [PS5, PS9, PS24].
COF5	Avoidance of scheduled meetings [PS2, PS21].
COF6	Structural and cultural barriers such as geographical distance, language differences, time zone gaps, and cultural diversity [PS9, PS21, PS24].
COF7	Absence of diversity-aware organizational policies [PS11, PS24, PS26].
COF8	Lack of shared norms to guide team member interactions [PS9, PS21, PS27].
COF9	Organizational or individual resistance to change [PS5, PS9, PS22].
COF10	Excess or lack of organizational formality [PS5, PS22].
COF11	Power structures or informal hierarchies that hinder participation [PS9, PS24, PS39].
COF12	Unequal perceptions regarding the importance of gender diversity [PS11, PS24, PS26].
COF13	Implicit, nonexplicit hierarchies [PS32, PS42].
COF14	Non-participatory, individualistic, or weak organizational cultures [PS3, PS9, PS24].
COF15	Managers' lack of understanding of team culture, which prevents inclusive management [PS3, PS24].
COF16	Low investment in essential human resources functions such as talent development, integration, and retention [PS3].
COF17	Recruitment errors that worsen cultural incompatibility and hinder new member integration [PS3, PS24].
COF18	Linguistic distance and unmanaged cultural diversity [PS21, PS24].
COF19	Organizational heterogeneity stemming from divergent cultural norms and values [PS24, PS27].
COF20	Lack of intercultural awareness and absence of mediating figures [PS24, PS21].
COF21	Organizational cultures that prioritize factors such as experience or team size over inclusion [PS11, PS32].
COF22	Lack of recognition or organizational support for team members [PS3, PS32].
COF23	Ongoing tensions between sub-teams caused by cultural, technical, or structural differences [PS21, PS27].
COF24	Unstable processes and poor decision-making [PS9, PS27].
COF25	Individualistic work culture [PS3, PS24].

Acronyms used: Cultural and Organizational Factor (COF).